

Guidelines for School Administration in COVID-19 Serious Condition of Primary School Administrators in Chonburi Province, Thailand

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Abstract

The purpose of this qualitative research was current condition, problems, and guidelines for school administration in COVID-19 serious condition of primary school administrators in Chonburi, Thailand. The Key informants using purposive sampling method were 30 school administrators in Chonburi province. Data collection by in-depth interview method using a semi-structured interview form created by the researcher. The data analysis was content analysis. The research findings showed that: The following was the learning and teaching management guidelines for school administrators during the outbreak: 1) The administrators have announced the deferral of the semester's start and finish dates, according to a Ministry of Education announcement; 2) Scheduling for compensation teaching for students who require it, particularly primary 6 students who will be taking the secondary 1 exam; 3) a variety of channels for communicating information to parents, instructors, and students; 4) Organizing online classes at a predetermined time; 5) Reducing the number of people who come to school each day by organizing school timetables that alternate between days and times; and 6) Setting up a mechanism for appropriate evaluating teaching. The following was the physical management: 1) The tables must be separated by at least one meter; 2) During meals, the distance between the students' seating arrangements 3) Before entering, students are screened by taking their temperature; and 4) Provide handwashing stations, hand soap, or enough alcohol gel for everyone in the school. The following was to monitor the behavior of everyone in the school to avoid the spread of the virus: 1) To prevent the virus from spreading, assign strict teachers to monitor everyone's behavior at the school; 2) Providing a policy for all teachers to monitor the behavior of all students in the school and, if any inappropriate behavior is discovered, to emphasize and advise them to correct it immediately; 3) Emphasizing on parents to help monitor the behavior of students at home; 4) Cultivating administrators, teachers, and parents to set a good example for students. The following was general administration: 1) All workers in educational institutions must be reminded to properly follow the Ministry of Health's guidelines; and 2) Put up sign to publicize the campaign to prevent the spread of COVID-19 thoroughly. The following was participatory management with the community: 1) Parents, community leaders, vendors, and others come together without being asked to help budget for schools in crisis; 2) Collaborate with community leaders to investigate the market and provide residents advice on how to act; and 3) The school relies on the participation of community leaders such as school administrators, Director of Tambon Health Promoting Hospital, parents, President of Sub-District Administrative Organization, the subdistrict headman, the village headman, and all members of the community. It must be remembered that keeping oneself safe from COVID-19 is everyone's responsibility, and it is not a cause to infect others.

Introduction

Thailand's educational system, the Ministry of Education is in charge of organizing it. From early childhood education to higher education, the government would take direct responsibility and provide possibilities for the private sector to participate in education. For compulsory education in Thailand, Thai citizens must complete at least lower secondary education and must be enrolled at the latest at the age of 7. This obligatory education is a part of basic education, which consists of six years of elementary school and six years of secondary school.

Early childhood education is also included in basic education. According to the Constitution of the Kingdom of Thailand, BE 2550, the state must provide thorough and high-quality services without charge (2007). In Thailand, formal education, non-formal education, and informal education are the three types of education available. As a result, educational institutions are the primary organizations that contribute to the development of high-quality individuals who will play a significant role in the country's development for it to catch up with other countries. The current Thai education system as defined in the National Education Act B.E. 2542 (1999) amended (No. 2) 2002, the 6-3-3 system is organized into six years of primary education (6 grade levels), three years of lower secondary education (3 grade levels), and three years of high school (3 grade levels). Thus, formal education, non-formal education, and informal education are the three types of education. The Ministry of Higher Education, Science, Research, and Innovation will be in charge of education administration and control at the higher education level [1]. 2021 (Ministry of Education).

From the beginning of 2020 to the present, there has been an epidemic of an emerging disease, or a new strain of influenza known as Corona Virus Disease 2019: COVID19, which has impacted the economy and society of many countries throughout the world, including Thailand, both directly and indirectly. To control the spread of the disease in Thailand, the government must take urgent measures such as refraining from domestic and international travel, social distance, adjusting working hours at home, refraining from providing entertainment, service places, restaurants, government offices, schools, universities, and so on. According to the most recent data as of June 10, 2021, there are 187,538 total people infected, 139,287 recovered, 46,876 in hospital, and 1375 dead [2]. Even if vaccines have begun to be brought in to be administered to patients, this is insufficient. The Ministry of Education has ordered the closure of all educational institutions, as well as the postponing of the start of the 2020 academic year from May 2563 to July 2563. In addition, the academic year 2021 has declared that the semester has been rescheduled from May 17 to June 1, 2021, from the initial date of May 17, 2021 [3]. However, due to the epidemic scenario of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 or COVID-19, which has resurfaced for the third time, there is no indication that the epidemic may be cured or reduced. As a result, the Ministry of Education must announce that the first semester of the academic year 2021 would be extended from June 1 to June 14, 2021. There is also a policy in place to prepare for teaching and learning that is appropriate for the scenario. For example, changing each course's teaching to be online, screening measures, and distance between students, wearing a mask, lowering the number of learners in each classroom, and so on [4] (Ministry of Education, 2020). As a result, various measures including individuals involved in education, such as teachers, students, and parents, must adjust to current and future situations. In addition, educational institution administrators must demonstrate leadership potential to manage educational institutions effectively, especially primary school, which is considered an important foundation for children to grow into quality adults in the future. They must understand how to manage educational institutions in order to achieve both teaching quality and successfully avoid the growth of COVID-19 in the classroom. Furthermore, educational institutions are located in the community and are associated to parents in the community, hence they are related to community health management.

Pattaya, a major Thai beach city, is located in the Chonburi Province. Many visitors visited the area a year before the epidemic. For example, in 2019, 18,211,539 tourists visited Chonburi, creating a total revenue of 264,543.05 baht. For example, in 2019, 18,211,539 tourists visited Chonburi, creating a total revenue of 264,543.05 baht. However, after the emergence of COVID-19, the government has declared the closure of tourist destinations, impacting a great number of people's economy and society [5] (Statistical report of Chonburi Province, 2019). Chonburi Province is a province that has been designated as a red zone that requires special attention. As of June 10, 2021, 4,789 cases of COVID-19 infection had been discovered, ranking 7th out of 76 provinces in Thailand [2]. The research team understands the significant of quality educational institution management and the prevention of COVID-19 spread for the quality of teaching and learning, which would affect the country's people development. As a result, we are interested studying about school administration guidelines in the primary school Covid-19 critical condition in Chonburi Province, Thailand. The result will be a more effective guidelines of managing primary education institutions, which will serve to improve the quality of life of instructors, children, parents, and Thai citizens.

Research Objectives

The objectives of this research article were to study the current conditions, problems, and guidelines for educational institution administration amid the COVID-19 of elementary school crisis in Thailand.

Method

The research is a qualitative research.

Key informants were 30 principals of primary schools under the government of Thailand. In qualitative study, key informants were chosen based on 20-30 key informants or until the data was saturated [6] (Creswell, 2013). Purposive sampling and the snowball technique are used to choose key informants, who consent to information on the condition that the sample group will not be harmed in any way and can withdraw at any time, even if the

research is still ongoing. Furthermore, in order to protect the rights of the informant group and to prevent negative effects on the informant group, the researcher will present the data using a pseudonym rather than the real name of the group of informants, consisting of P1 representing key informant 1, P2 representing key informant 2, and so on.

The Research Instrument

The instruments used in this research were the researcher and the semi-structured interview form. Because of qualitative research, researchers are important tools for data collection. Therefore, the researcher has to prepare before going to the real area by preparing content knowledge, qualitative research methodology by self-reading of textbooks, works, and related research to cover the issues for the interview.

Data Collection Method

Data were collected from 30 key informants using an in-depth interview method or until the data was saturated. Other data collection methods, such as observation and field note, were also included.

Data Analysis

The patient's personal data were analyzed by frequency distribution method. During the COVID-19 crisis of elementary school in Thailand, content analysis was used to analyze the information on educational institution management guidelines with community participation. The data is coded, translated, and interpreted, and concepts are created in comparison to previously investigated theories and study outcomes based on content analysis. Furthermore, computer programs aid in the organization of the data analysis system. According to [7] Strauss and Corbin (1998), data analysis consists of three steps:

1. Open coding is the process of coding or indexing based on the information collected from the interview [8] (SuphangChantavanich, 2008), which is a congruence analysis reflecting the type or group of data obtained from the interview. The researcher considers opening the code with reading it line by line. If there is any message indicating the guidelines for the management of educational institutions during the Covid-19 crisis of primary schools in Thailand for research purposes, the researcher will code the message.

2. Axial coding is the process of coding that combines the processing of data types and data type properties together. It is the first step in establishing the relationship between each code's data.

3. Select coding is the process of selecting events that is the key leading to the conclusion of the findings of decoding from the information obtained from the interview. It is the process of bringing types and relationships or the core of the data to summarize the relationship characteristics or the phenomena of educational institution management guidelines in the context of the COVID-19 crisis in primary schools in Thailand.

Examining the Reliability and Validity of Data (Rigor criteria)

The researcher uses a method of examining the same information from multiple sources (Data Triangulation), such as annual reports, newspapers, analysis of related documents, etc. After gathering the data, a reflexive note is recorded after collecting the data to record the ideas, beliefs based on information, and the link found in the data collection to be used to analyze the data completely and accurately.

Results and Discussion

The following findings were presented in accordance with the research objectives: During the Covid-19 Crisis of the Chonburi Province primary school, administrators will be informed about the behaviors and various measures from the Ministry of Education, such as screening students before entering school, social distancing, wearing a mask, frequently using hand sanitizer, and so on. In addition, the information about the practice is communicated to teachers, students, and parents regularly by using a variety of communication channels to reach the target audience as much as possible, as stated by an informant.

“During the initial COVID-19 outbreak, schools had a method, measures to protect by publicizing information to students and parents. There is a voice message on the line, document to notify parents directly, and because we are the red area, there will be measures to wear masks, hand washing with alcohol gel.”

School classrooms are cleaned by spraying disinfectants, and screening students by measuring their body temperature before entering school. It is consistent with the statement of an informant.

“Classrooms are cleaned and disinfected for parents' peace of mind. There are daily temperature checks and quarantines for high-risk groups by consulting with Tambon Health Promoting Hospital.”

Schools have physical management in place to reduce the risk of infection, such as providing more hand wash basins, maintaining a distance of at least 1 meter, arranging tables far apart, dining tables, etc., preparing alcohol gel, and providing enough hand washing, which is consistent with an informant who stated.

“We'll need to prepare alcohol gel, install more sinks, and make sure they're at least 1 meter apart.”

Schools coordinate the sub-district health promoting hospitals to provide knowledge on hand washing, prevention of the spread of COVID-19 in schools, in agreement with an informant who said.

“The Tambon Health Promoting Hospital will also demonstrate how to wash your hands properly. The students will also be randomly tested to see how effectively they wash their hands.”
Educating teachers about COVID-19 in the early days of the outbreak, teachers learn about COVID-19 from television news, most online media which is consistent with an informant's statement.

“I know from various media such as TV lines that the disease is caused by a virus produced by bats, which then spreads to animals, and the man brought the infected animal and ate it. Therefore, the infection spreads from person to person together in the initial stage. Because it is a new virus, so there is no definitive treatment. In addition, this infection enters Thailand by foreigners which the infection will show symptoms after 14 days which, before you know it, can infect many others.”

Teachers are informed about COVID-19 prevention practices, which is consistent with an informant's statement.

“People should always wear a mask at all times, carry alcohol to wash your hands all the time, and reduce or refrain from unnecessary visits to the community. If necessary, there will be protection at all times.”

All community teams, including sub-district health promoting hospitals, sub-district administrative organizations, schools, police, village health volunteers, subdistrict headmen, and village headmen, went to inspect the market in the community. They also find students wearing masks incorrectly such as on the chin, and give the right advise which is consistent with an informant's statement.

“There is a community team that inspects the flea market every day, including the director of the Tambon Health Promoting Hospital, the school director, the sub-district Administrative Organization, the village health volunteers, the subdistrict headman, the village headman, and the police. Most individuals wear masks, but few people put on the chin, especially students. When the team finds them, they recommend them to place it in the right position.”

Problems and Obstacles Encountered

Parents are worried that their children will not be able to complete their study on time because the situation is unprecedented, and difficult to manage. When the school announces, the students must stop studying or postpone the start of classes to reduce the number of meetings or mass gatherings according to the measures of the state, parents are concerned that their children will be unable to learn. Parents do not have time to take care of their children at home, because they are out to work, mostly in agriculture. Students do not have technology to study, which is consistent with an informant.

“Education management has not been the same before. Young children cannot study online. Primary school students are not ready. Parents also pay attention to their children because they are worried that their children will not be able to complete their study on time. Some families do not have someone to take care of their children at home. Furthermore, the grandchildren who live with their grandparents will be unable to comprehend the usage of technology. During the initial outbreak, school will be suspended for about a month.”

Online studying makes it difficult to interact and observe facial expressions causing inability to assess learners' feelings as accurately as possible. As a result, teaching planning may not meet the needs of students which is consistent with an informant's statement.

“Studying in the classroom is better than studying online because it is able to interact. However, the main thing for online studying is family and technological readiness. Moreover, teachers are unable to observe the facial expressions, gestures, and feelings of students because the class teaching design must be suitable for the students as well.”

Students are concerned over privacy because the surveillance measures for the spread of the virus in schools require teachers to always monitor their behavior, such as monitoring wearing masks, washing hands, social distancing, and so on. It is consistent with what an informant said.

“The majority of problems will be related to a loss of privacy. Sometimes children feel uncomfortable being controlled, being watched for safety, which many people feel uncomfortable.”

Solutions

When a problem arises, use teamwork, consult the supervisor, gradually solve the problem, and confidence in each person's abilities, which is consistent with what an informant said.

“There is no reason to discouraged. If there is a problem, we work to solve it gradually because every problem has a solution, whether how slow or quickly. We work as a team. There are adults who on hand to give advice. Everyone has different abilities and can help each other.”

The schools request cooperation from all parties to take full responsibility for their own duties, including sub-district health promotion hospitals that provide knowledge about COVID-19. Teachers serve as role models and give advice to students. Students should practice correctly and honestly, if you have symptoms, they should consult a doctor, give a real personal information, and treat as a new normal life habit which is consistent with an informant's statement.

“Everyone gives collaborate and protect themselves together. If symptoms are discovered, immediately see a doctor. Not to be ignore, and must give a true personal information, as well as always be a new normal. If there is a complete vaccine, everyone deserves it.”

Everyone is requested to keep clean, particularly while living together which is consistent with an informant who said.

"I would like to emphasize cleanliness. Overall, when many people are together, there will be problems with cleanliness. Therefore, I would like to leave everyone involved to assist in this matter."

During the epidemic, there is compensatory instructional management after school breaks, which is consistent with an informant's statement.

"There is only studying issue here. There are students from the level of Kindergarten to Primary 6. However, remedial lessons would be provided for students in primary 6 in order to prepare them for admission exams to the secondary 1."

The budget is not a problem because the people, parents donate money to buy additional protective equipment which is consistent with an informant's statement.

"Parents come to send their children and see that they don't have alcohol gel and donate them, community leaders, wealthy people in the community, sellers, donate among themselves without being asked."

During the outbreak, here are guidelines for school administration. From the above information, the researcher summarizes the guidelines for the administration of educational institutions during the COVID-19 outbreak as follows:

Management of teaching and learning: 1) The administrators have announced the deferral of the semester's start and finish dates, according to a Ministry of Education announcement; 2) Scheduling for compensation teaching for students who require it, particularly primary 6 students who will be taking the secondary 1 exam; 3) A variety of channels for communicating information to parents, instructors, and students; 4) Organizing online classes at a predetermined time; 5) Reducing the number of people who come to school each day by organizing school timetables that alternate between days and times; and 6) Setting up a mechanism for appropriate evaluating teaching.

The physical management: 1) The tables must be separated by at least one meter; 2) During meals, the distance between the students' seating arrangements 3) Before entering, students are screened by taking their temperature; and 4) Provide hand washing stations, hand soap, or enough alcohol gel for everyone in the school.

To monitor the behavior of everyone in the school to avoid the spread of the virus: 1) To prevent the virus from spreading, assign strict teachers to monitor everyone's behavior at the school; 2) Providing a policy for all teachers to monitor the behavior of all students in the school and, if any inappropriate behavior is discovered, to emphasize and advise them to correct it immediately; 3) Emphasizing on parents to help monitor the behavior of students at home; 4) Cultivating administrators, teachers, and parents to set a good example for students.

General administration: 1) All workers in educational institutions must be reminded to properly follow the Ministry of Health's guidelines; and 2) Put up sign to publicize the campaign to prevent the spread of COVID-19 thoroughly.

Participatory management with the community: 1) Parents, community leaders, vendors, and others come together without being asked to help budget for schools in crisis; 2) Collaborate with community leaders to investigate the market and provide residents advice on how to act; and 3) The school relies on the participation of community leaders such as school administrators, Director of Tambon Health Promoting Hospital, parents, President of Sub-District Administrative Organization, the subdistrict headman, the village headman, and all members of the community. It must be remembered that keeping oneself safe from COVID-19 is everyone's responsibility, and it is not a cause to infect others.

Discussions

The researcher discussed the results according to the following interesting issues: Issues of education institution administration in form of government

According to the findings of the study, school administrators in Chonburi Province's primary schools will be informed about the conduct and various measures enacted by the Ministry of Education during the COVID-19 crisis. This is because schools of study are a government agency; therefore, schools are unable to make independent decisions. They must strictly comply with government regulations. Failure to comply or work before the government announcement to the school will result in serious punishments for the administrators. It is in accordance with the Rules of Government Teachers and Educational Personnel B.E. 2547 Section 86 [9], which states that Government teachers and education personnel must comply with the orders of the superiors which are in accordance with the law and government regulations without resisting or avoiding. However, if it is considered that compliance with the order will damage the government or will not serve the interests of the government, the officers may submit an opinion in writing within seven days for the supervisor to review the order. When an opinion is presented, subordinates must comply if the supervisor confirms in writing to follow the original order. Disobeying or avoiding obeying orders from supervisors who have ordered in accordance with the law and government regulations, causing serious damage to the government service, is a serious disciplinary offense. This is a reason of this research found that the guidelines for the management of

educational institutions during the COVID-19 outbreak. It is also a bureaucratic style with a command structure that is hierarchical.

Issues of school administration amid concerns in the Covid-19 situation

According to the findings of the study, the administrators stated that it was difficult to manage because it is an unprecedented event. This is due to the COVID-19 epidemic situation, which is an emerging disease, that has never happened before. In addition, it is easily spread through droplet transmission, contact, and inhalation of pathogens that can cause lung disease and impair the function of the respiratory system. If not treated promptly, it can lead to death. For more than a year, there has been an outbreak. Thailand currently has a daily number of infections, and deaths are on the rise. It is consistent with the Human Resource for Health Research and Development Office in the future (2020), which said that Thailand has been facing this strange coronavirus named Covid-19 for more than a year. When the number of outbreaks is counted, there are two major waves, with a third wave on the way. The third wave of British strain outbreaks serve as a reminder that existing vaccines may not be able to handle it even when a portion of the population has already been vaccinated. However, based on the situation both inside and outside the country, it is easy to assume that Covid-19 will remain with us for a long time. Thailand has previously had outbreaks of avian flu, SARS, and MERS, so this is not the country's first encounter with new diseases. But this time, if looking at the disease control, it is considered much more frightening than before. From the above reasons, the administrators of the school believe that managing the school in the COVID-19 situation is difficult.

Issues of parents concerned about their children's ineffectiveness in schools.

When the school announces that the students must stop studying or postpone the start of classes in order to reduce the meetings or mass gathering according to the measures of the state make parents worried. Parents do not have time to take care of their children at home because they have to work outside, mostly agriculture, and students do not have access to technology to study. This is because the school studied at this time was a primary school level in Thailand which is located in rural areas. Because farming is the primary occupation of the parents, the daily routine consists of getting up early to cook, clothe the children, and deliver them to school. After that, they went to a farm. He returned in the evening to take the children home, so it seems that there was no time to be at home during the day. When there is a pandemic situation of COVID-19, the school has announced that students will not be able to attend classes but will allow online learning from home with the support of their parents. Therefore, it is difficult and stressful for parents because they do not have time to spend with their children all day. Furthermore, most parents do not have the technological tools for their children to study online because they do not have enough money to get them. This is consistent with the study of [10], which found that teaching approaches during the Covid-19 period have a significant impact on the education system including online learning problems, teaching, assignments, and follow-up assessment. It also found that there should be a platform to support the study of the new normal lifestyle system so that it is ready for everyone and more thoroughly. Because of such reasons, parents are worried that their children will not be able to complete their study on time and not as effective as they should be.

Issues of school management with participation in the community

According to the findings, all community teams, namely the Tambon Health Promoting Hospital, the Administrative Organization, schools, police, village health volunteers, the subdistrict headman, and the village headman, went to inspect the market to monitor the implementation of the Covid-19 epidemic prevention policy regarding wearing masks, regular hand washing. They found that students wear masks by putting on the chin, so they recommend them to place it in the right position. It is a cooperation because primary schools in Thai communities are located in communities. Community leaders are the administrators of the community who are members of the community, and it is more sustainable by adhering to the principle of community care for each other. Therefore, everyone who has the main responsibility in the community and the people must come together because they know the problems of the community better than anyone else. It is consistent with the study of [11] found that promoting volunteer health village participation in proactive disease surveillance. Proactive surveillance and prevention of COVID-19 infection by community participation is an important strategy to stop the disease's spread. Therefore, it is a challenge for all sectors involved in disease prevention operations to continue taking action and expanding the application to effectively and effectively prevent diseases that are important problems of the country, especially with problematic conditions and spatial contexts. From the reasons, the school administrators run schools in the form of community participation.

Conclusion

The current state of school administration during of the COVID-19 crisis of Chonburi Province primary school, the administrators will be informed about the behavior and various measures issued by the Ministry of Education. Then Schools regularly communicate information about their conduct to teachers, students, and parents, and they use a variety of communication channels to reach the target audience as much as possible. Before entering school, students are screened by measuring their body temperature, and classrooms are cleaned more frequently. There is physical management in place to reduce the risk of infection such as providing more

hand wash basins, separating meal seats and classroom tables by at least 1 meter, preparing alcohol gel, and sanitizing enough hand washing. The schools have the participation of every community team in monitoring the practice of people in the community, such as the Tambon Health Promoting Hospital, the director of sub-district Administrative Organization, schools, police, the village health volunteers, the subdistrict headman, and the village headman. The community team walks to inspect the market in the community. Then they found that the students were not wearing the right masks such as hanging on the chin; therefore, gave the proper advice.

Problems and Obstacles Encountered

Problems and obstacles were found that: Parents are concerned that their children will not be able to complete their studies on time during school breaks. There is no one at home to care for the children during school breaks because their parents have to go to work in agriculture. There is lack of technology knowledge to help teaching children during school breaks through Zoom, and there are no computer or online learning materials for children to study at home.

Recommendations

A. Recommendations for Practices

1. According to the study's findings, the administration of primary schools under the Ministry of Education which is the Thai government; therefore, administrators always must wait for orders from the authorities before changing or doing various responsibilities. Any decisions that are made in an emergency for the performance of the work are not as good as they should be. Therefore, it is proposed that the Ministry of Education should have an urgent management channel that is somewhat flexible from the government regulations in order to be a channel for the administrators of primary schools, who are closest to the people, to operate more efficiently up.

2. According to the study's findings, community-based school administrators are an important principle that can help solving the problem initially, especially the budget that the community contributes to the purchase of Covid-19 prevention equipment to schools in times of crisis without being asked. Therefore, it is proposed that educational policy makers develop participatory administration of primary schools to make the system stronger and more acceptable.

B. Recommendations for Further Research

1. Should conduct a quantitative research on factors affecting the school administration in crisis.

2. Should study the appropriate measures in the administration of primary and secondary schools in Thailand and compare them with other countries.

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